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Data management plan (DMP)

Programming Language Ecosystem Project

[PLEP]

Version	Effective date	Description of document/changes
1.0	13/10/2023	First version of DMP – created for start of project

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List of acronyms

DMP	data management plan
RDM	research data management

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Introduction

Science Europe practical guide, FAIR data

A DMP is a structured document that keeps record of what research data is created and what happens to that data during and after a project. It helps with planning the research process and defining responsibilities in a research project involving several researchers or institutions.

For writing this DMP, we followed [the recommendations of Science Europe](#) as they reflect the guidelines agreed upon by the major funders in Europe.

To make our data FAIR, they generally will be treated according to the following criteria:

- We will make our data findable, by uploading it to a data repository that provides a persistent identifier, and adding relevant metadata.
- We will make our data accessible by providing open access to data, wherever possible. In cases, where open access is not possible, we will provide meaningful metadata plus contact information for access requests.
- We will make our data interoperable by providing and describing data in a way that is common within our domain by using the same file formats, schemas and vocabularies. We will provide good documentation for all our datasets.
- We will make our data reusable by adding metadata and comprehensive Readme files to all published datasets. The descriptions include details on the methodology used, analytical and procedural information. In case of publication, licenses for code and data will always be assigned and clearly marked.

Relevant Policies and Guidelines

- TU Wien Policy for Research Data Management: <https://www.tuwien.at/index.php?eID=dms&s=4&path=Directives%20and%20Regulations%20of%20the%20Rectorate/Policy%20for%20Research%20Data%20Management.pdf>
- TU Wien Code of Conduct – Rules to Ensure Good Scientific Practice: <https://www.tuwien.at/index.php?eID=dms&s=4&path=Directives%20and%20Regulations%20of%20the%20Rectorate/Code%20of%20Conduct%20E2%80%93%20Rules%20to%20Ensure%20Good%20Scientific%20Practice.pdf>
- Directives and Regulations of the TU Wien Rectorate: <https://www.tuwien.at/en/tu-wien/organisation/central-divisions/data-protection-and-document-management/directives-regulations/>
- TU Wien Data Protection: <https://www.tuwien.at/en/tu-wien/organisation/central-divisions/data-protection-and-document-management/data-protection-at-tu-wien>

1. Data description

1a Lists of datasets that will be reused or produced

Produced datasets

dataset ID	title	type	format	estimated volume	contains sensitive data
P1	usage_of_programming_languages_2011-2023	Structured text	csv	100 MB	no

Reused datasets

dataset ID	title	PID (e.g. DOI) or source	rights (e.g. license)	contains sensitive data
R1	stack_overflow_developer_survey	https://insights.stackoverflow.com/survey	ODbL	no
R2	PYPL_survey_2004-2023	https://github.com/pypl/pypl.github.io/tree/master	CC BY 3.0	no
R3	github_metadata	https://www.kaggle.com/datasets/pelmers/github-repository-metadata-with-5-stars/	CC BY 4.0	no

1b Data generation and reuse

Methods and software used for data generation and reuse

The three reused datasets are going to be analyzed and the result will be the usage_of_programming_languages_2011-2023.csv dataset. To achieve the knowledge extraction from the datasets, a python script will be used, it is available on github under <https://github.com/ValentinFutterer/UsageOfProgramminglanguages2011-2023?tab=readme-ov-file>. This script is going to do a lot of the heavy lifting, since the input datasets have vastly different formats. The PYPL_survey_2004-2023, for example, is a js file. The source code is freely available under an MIT license.

2. Documentation and data quality

2a Data organisation, metadata and documentation

The filenames will follow the projects naming convention as seen on github. There will be only one version of the endproduct P1. If someone wants to reproduce the data, he/she can do so themselves easily via the source code on github <https://github.com/ValentinFutterer/UsageOfProgramminglanguages2011-2023?tab=readme-ov-file>.

As there are no domain specific metadata standards applicable, we will provide a README file with an explanation of all values and terms used. This explanation can be found on github <https://github.com/ValentinFutterer/UsageOfProgramminglanguages2011-2023?tab=readme-ov-file> or in the TU Wien repository <https://test.researchdata.tuwien.ac.at/records/gnbse-ts649>. This will help others to identify, discover and reuse our data.

Additionally, we will provide common metadata such as title, description or keywords when publishing data in open access repositories. In such a case, we will follow the default template provided by the repository, such as Data Cite Metadata or Dublin Core.

As far as possible, we will use controlled vocabularies for our data to allow inter-disciplinary interoperability and machine-actionability.

The documentation is in form of a github repository, which can be found at <https://github.com/ValentinFutterer/UsageOfProgramminglanguages2011-2023?tab=readme-ov-file>. Anything to reproduce the experiment can be found there, including the original datasets used to produce the result.

2b Data quality control

The following data quality checks will be done: peer review of data.

3. Storage and backup during research process

3a Storage and backup facilities

For the duration of the project, storage and backup of data will be ensured by the project manager in cooperation with the responsible representative of TU.it. The infrastructure of TU Wien will be used for this purpose.

R1 (stack_overflow_developer_survey), R2 (PYPL_survey_2004-2023), R3 (github_metadata) will be stored in Github, since they are not the end result of the project. They are also accessible on their original source as linked in this document.

P1 (usage_of_programming_languages_2011-2023) will be stored in TUownCloud: TUownCloud is a sync&share service provided by TU.it for TU Wien members. It runs on TU.it servers and offers features known from public cloud systems such as Dropbox, for example, the exchange of data with authorized persons. Deleted files can be recovered within 180 days.

3b Data security and protection of sensitive data

We pay strict attention to compliance with the relevant institutional and national data protection policies listed in the introduction of this document. At this stage, it is not foreseen to process any sensitive data in the project. If this changes, advice will be sought from the data protection specialist at TU Wien (Verena Dolovai), and the DMP will be updated.

Access to data during research:

dataset ID	selected project members	all other project members	the public
P1	reading only	reading only	reading only
R1	reading only	reading only	reading only
R2	reading only	reading only	reading only
R3	reading only	reading only	reading only

All incidents will be handled individually by an incident response team that is maintaining the affected service.

4. Legal and ethical requirements

4a Personal data

At this stage, it is not foreseen to process any personal data in the project. If this changes, advice will be sought from the data protection specialist at TU Wien (Verena Dolovai), and the DMP will be updated.

4b Intellectual property rights and ownership

Legal restrictions on how data is processed and shared are specified in the <https://opendatacommons.org/licenses/odbl/1-0/> license. The restrictions relate to datasets P1 (usage_of_programming_languages_2011-2023), and R1 (stack_overflow_developer_survey). Since P1 falls under the ODbl, derivative work, like R1 has to be published under R1, which is still preferable to not having a license, since then it would have been unusable.

stack_overflow_developer_survey is owned by stackoverflow and usage_of_programming_languages-2011-2023 is owned by TU Wien. TU Wien has rights to the produced data and controls access.

4c Ethical issues

No particular ethical issue is foreseen with the data to be used or produced by the project. This section will be updated if issues arise.

5. Data sharing and long-term preservation

5a Data publication and access conditions

As far as possible, obtained datasets will be published in repositories. Details on access conditions, reuse licenses, reasons for restrictions, etc. are collected in the table below.

dataset ID	access conditions	restrictions / embargo reasons	estimated publication date	location for publication (repository)	PID	license
P1	Open	Open Data Commons Open Database License (ODbL) license	2023-10-13	TU Wien Research Data	https://test.researchdata.tuwien.ac.at/reports/gnbse-ts649	ODbL

The repositories used in this project are described in the following paragraph:

TU Wien Research Data is an institutional repository of TU Wien to enable storing, sharing and publishing of digital objects, in particular research data. It facilitates the funders' requirements for open access to research data and the FAIR principles by making research output findable, accessible, interoperable, and reusable. A DOI is assigned to each dataset published in TU Wien Research Data. This service is developed by the TU Wien Center for Research Data Management and hosted by TU.it. <https://researchdata.tuwien.at/>

5b Long-term preservation and deletion of data

dataset ID	location for long-term storage	minimum retention period (≥ 10 years)	foreseeable research uses and/or users
P1	TU Wien Research Data	10 years	Members of the scientific community

6. RDM responsibilities and resources

6a RDM-roles and responsibilities

Valentin Futterer will direct the data management process overall, with the research assistants responsible for ensuring metadata production, day-to-day cross-checks, back-up and other quality control activities are maintained.

6b Resources

There are no costs dedicated to data management and ensuring that data will be FAIR.